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CE4T – CLEAN ENERGY FOR TOURISM

“With the project CE4T we are contributing substantially to decarbonising and increasing the efficiency of the winter tourism sector. The aim is to generate the technologies and systems in such a way that they can also be used in other industrial sectors. We thus provide significant added value for further applications. For Salzburg AG this is a further opportunity to be a future-oriented partner for our customers by developing new services and products.”

NORBERT DORFINGER, Project Manager CE4T, Salzburg AG

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The innovative approach of ‘Clean Energy for Tourism‘ consists in the integrative, systemic optimization of the three central areas of electricity supply, electricity market and large consumers. CE4T is developing optimization algorithms, related interfaces and an ICT framework to maximize energy efficiency and renewable energy integration, and to leverage flexibility options for both the electricity and energy needs of the tourism industry.

KEY FACTS

Duration: 10/18 - 09/22

Project volume: € 4,022 Mio.

MAIN GOALS

Decarbonization of the winter tourism industry using state-of-the-art digitization technology and new optimization algorithms

Development of optimization algorithms to demonstrate and exploit the required flexibilities at all levels and enable integrated system-wide optimization

Setting up of an energy monitoring including automatic optimization algorithms to increase energy efficiency, decarbonisation of energy supply and integration of renewable energy production units in the overall system

